

Continuous Controlling Vacuum in Accelerator

Jihyeon Yoon*
(Mabangjin Software)

December 5, 2022

Abstract

This paper aims to suggest method for sustaining vacuum in particle accelerator while in an variety of circumstances.

1 Introduction

Current observation in particle accelerator could be improved by giving different condition in making vacuum space, likewise in LHC[1].

2 Purpose of Vacuum

The most problem caused in vacuum space as an error is because of irregular scattering toward the observation target. Then two methods could be suggested.

1. Maximizing vacuum
2. Organizing vacuum

While attempt of “maximizing vacuum” has been done so far, organizing vacuum has been discussed a little. Then how to organize a vacuum? The suggestion is in an eye of hurricane.

Outside convection flows from low pressure (bottom) to high pressure (top) around the eye of the hurricane, but inside the eye of the hurricane, low pressure with little difference in internal convection has a stable flow.

State of vacuum assumes no convection flow in overall. However, if it is an accelerator (or observation) situation that requires fine adjustment, even in this vacuum, convection cannot be avoided. So giving condition in vacuum by organizing like:

Figure 1: Convection flow of hurricane [2]

*Jihyeon Yoon is a korean medicine doctor. And he is a freelance programmer also.
E-mail: flyingtext@nate.com
Yeongdeungpo-gu, Seoul, 07429,
Seoul, South Korea
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9610-0994>

3 Suggestion of micro-pipelining in vacuum

Suggesting method to be configured in a torus shape of:

Figure 2: Giving consistent vacuum by micro pipeline

By giving vacuum state differently by inner pipeline and outer covering pipeline which is connected with micro pipeline, vacuum state could be steadily maintained. Micro pipelines act as cirrus shield in convection of hurricane and pull out adequate amount of vacuum steadily, while the outer pipeline gives amount of vacuum in exchange consistency. And also for sure, alternative implementation shape could be possible with sustaining the main idea.

4 Limitations and Conclusions

1. Convection inside high vacuum seems be controllable with adapting micro-pipelining.
2. By utilizing this method, even in a situation of running acceleration could operate vacuum system.
3. Although the size and utilization of micro-pipeline should be more to be discussed and calculated, mainly in an idea from hurricane could be a original as from a perspective of mimesis from nature.

References

- [1] O. Gröbner, "Overview of the LHC vacuum system," *Vacuum*, vol. 60, no. 1-2, pp. 25-34, 2001, publisher: Elsevier.
- [2] Kelvinsong, "English: Diagram of a hurricane." Dec. 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Hurricane-en.svg>